

**PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF
LOW COST HOUSING CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN
NAIROBI CITY COUNTY, KENYA**

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2023

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Keywords; Project Management Plan; Implementation; Low cost housing, Construction Projects;

Abstract

Implementation of low cost housing project that has been overhyped in Nairobi City County has borne very limited fruits as thousands of the City population still remain either homeless or lack decent housing as expressed through mushrooming of informal settlements in the City's residential areas. The general objective was to establish influence project management plan on implementation of low cost housing construction projects in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The study was anchored by system theory. Descriptive survey research design was used targeting a population of 299 contractors and project managers. A sample of 176 project managers and contractors were selected to participate in the study. The researcher used simple random and stratified sampling technique to determine the number of contractors and project managers and to select as participants from each sub group. Structured questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data. Internal reliability and consistency of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach's alpha and set at 0.700. Also construct, content and face validity was tested to ensure the instruments were adequate. The field data was analysed by use of descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings thereafter have been presented in Tables. The study established; that implementation of low cost housing construction projects do not demonstrate good progress as respectively demonstrated by composite mean and S.D of 2.65 and 1.322. A significant strong positive correlation was established between project management plan and implementation of low cost housing construction projects ($r=0.693$; $P<0.000$) with a composite mean and S.D 3.64; 1.284. The study concluded that project management plan has a positive significant influence on the implementation of low-cost housing projects and subsequently recommendation project management plan be used and applied as a reference and a guide to all low cost housing construction projects activities.

Introduction

Implementation of low cost housing is aimed at meeting the desired development goals as enshrined in the SDG number 11 and also the vision 2030 in Kenya (Ajulu,2019). Housing being a key pillar and a fundamental need for humans must thus be made affordable, adequate, safe and habitable to meet the needs by providing comfort to the inhabitants, (UN-Habitat 2012). Housing project is considered affordable and low cost if it's a purchase and acquisition cost or rental charges are not in excess of 30% of the family total monthly income as described by the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development.

In the USA around the mid-19th century, there was a critical need for low cost housing spurring the proliferation of low-cost housing in the undeveloped cities by the government as a policy response to the need. The projects were driven by the principle of housing the poor at a low cost through a trade-off between structural strength and attractiveness of the constructed houses, (Wainer, Ndengeyingoma, and Murray, 2016). The low cost housings were constructed in less desirable locations and this lowered the demand and subsequently the housing costs. The low cost housing projects were thus constructed in satellite Greenfields with limited and low land-use potential leading to low costs and limited social amenities. The housing projects had unattractive designs, unattractiveness and low aesthetic values. The low cost housing projects in USA for instance the *Pruit Igoe* project of 1954 utilized cheap building materials that met the structural standard-threshold of quality but with unwanted aesthetic quality standard thresholds. In as far as low cost housing projects were executed to solve the housing-deficit challenges in US, the disorienting issues were around meeting the architects' design and balancing it with low economic threshold cost and quality (Bertaud 2015)

Asia has a population of over 0.5 billion inhabiting majorly the urban centres, which call the need to meet the high demand for housing, an obligation that primarily should be met by the government because of low income classes of the inhabitants of southern and central Asia. In Indonesia for example one million housing project was initiated in 2015 to alleviate the housing projects with the shortage of housing estimated at about over 11 Million (Bernstein et al 2016). The government of Malaysia initiated RIMA housing projects in 2015 with the aim to solve the major housing challenges in her cities (Metcalf, 2018). The project was designed construct a housing units at a cost between \$23,000 and 94,000. Although passed significantly successful, the deficit was not eliminated and that prompted policy shift in order to aid private developers through PPPs to come in and supplement the government efforts. In Singapore her housing project initiatives became fairly successful in the implementation of low cost housing projects with Housing & Development Board created in the 1960 achieving a success rate of over 80% in housing the low income citizens, (Hemble,2019). The Vietnamese the government provided a stimulus package amounting to \$1.32 billion in order to promote low cost housing sector to the sector players, with Cambodian government, through her 2014 National Housing Policy focusing to construct a total of 1.1M housing units by 2030, (Asian Development Bank, 2020).

In Africa a number of low cost housing concepts have been adopted by different countries to meet the sky-rocketing demands created by rapid urbanization in the continent. South Africa's MMA Architects for instance innovated a concept with two-story houses being constructed with earth bags mounted in steel and wooden frame-columns. Earth blocks compressed and compacted were used to create to provide low-cost housing alternatives in the country. Fired earthen bricks have also been widely used in Rwanda for low cost housing construction projects in addition to the use

of recycled coffee husks. Through PPPs Angola has been able to provide over 200,000 low-cost housing units under the CITIC Construction Limited programmes in just under four years. In Ethiopia social housing programmes which was ambitiously launched in 2015 was able to provide low cost housing to her urban population and projected to run up to 2025. The projects though were not able to provide entirely and meet the demand for housing in the country, (Alamy, 2017).

About 70% of the urban dwellers Kenya do not have access to decent, safe, habitable and affordable housing and are thus are forced to move into informal housing settlement alternatives. With the average cost of housing units for a family in Nairobi being about Ksh. 11.5M which is way too high for the average population of developing countries in the world. Kenya's urban population growth is much faster than her capita GDP growth, leading to social ills like mushrooming of informal settlements, crime, unemployment, prostitution, traffic jams, pollutions and general social disorders in the urban areas. With a projected housing deficit of about 2 million units as at 2020, in the urban areas, Kenya has to find a solution or else be doomed into mushrooming of slums and unplanned settlements. This unfortunate situation has also been observed in many other African cities in the ranks of Dar es Salaam, Kigali, Cairo, Kampala, Tripoli Abuja, among others, (World Bank Publications, 2009). Nigeria in particular has a demand level of about 17 Million units to meet her current deficits which is rapidly growing too. Kenya though has used an expanded polystyrene panels (EPS) as a technology to construct low cost housing as cheaper building materials alternative to conventional stones, this too has failed to meet the demands for the housing which remains high due to her exponential population growth rate. The study thus sought to establish the influence of project management plan on implementation of low cost housing in Nairobi City

Problem Statement

Implementation of low cost housing projects that has been overhyped in Nairobi City County has borne very limited fruits as thousands of the City population still remain either homeless or lack decent housing expressed through mushrooming of informal settlements in the City's residential areas. It is projected that Nairobi City needs to bridge the deficit of over 2 Million low-cost housing to able to provide housing for the low income population and this demand is sky-rocketing driven by population growth that is so rapid in the city and exacerbated by rural urban migration. The government initiated a programme to construct low cost housing in the last decade however how could a citizen earning an average of Ksh. 10,000 as net income afford to own a house costing a minimum of Ksh. 3 Million, and as high as 10Million? (World Bank Report 2019). The answer is simply not possible and therefore the government needs to shift her policy on how to house her citizenry lest the slumming of the city grows to reach unprecedented magnitude.

In Kenya, private estate developing companies have reported very low occupancy rates leading to losses because of unaffordability driven by unfavorable tax regimes and policies from the government as housing units sometimes go up to 5 years after completion without any occupancy owing to unaffordability. In trying to create affordable low cost housing in Kenya, sub-standard building materials have been used in the process leading to collapse of in excess of 50 buildings since 2010 and that has ignited the debate of how safe are the low cost buildings? Several other low cost housing projects have simply become white elephant projects with millions of shillings already pumped into them due to economic and market feasibility related issues but no returns just yet. The real estate industry has been on the receiving end due to the effects of COVID-19 and the

economic recession the has swept across the global economies in the recent years leading to more failures than successes.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on systems theory

The theory was formulated in the 1940s by Ludwig von Bertalanffy. The theory states that systems relate to one another within a larger more sophisticated system. It further propagates that smaller systems interact together to run more complex systems with larger parts and complex structure and higher degree of combining power. The theory application requires an examination of all integrating parts of the smaller systems and effectively merging them to produce the desired products and results. This also include combining the resource for production to get the desired outputs.

This theory was important to this study because project management plan is like a system with different components working as small independent systems but combining to achieve the overall goal of the projects. There are systems for project stakeholders, suppliers, beneficiaries, proponents, implementation teams each separately focusing on their independent roles but collectively contributing to the overall project implementation goal. A system that is cohesive produces better results while a system disjointed cannot perform leading to system breakdown and subsequently stalled projects.

Empirical Reviews

Project Management Plan and Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

Project planning should be an essential component portion of the construction building projects sector in order to obtain more effective accomplishment of a development and have an effect on deliverables. Arief and Latief (2021) conducted research on improving the project management plan in a residential development project. The research attempted to parse the risks in residential housing planning phase by classifying 10 knowledge zones and 24 strategic planning in the 2017 PMBOK using a qualitative risk analysis technique to gain a better comprehension and mitigate the significant risk aspect. Based on the research findings, a preventative measures action plan for each high risk predictor has been developed and necessary to be incorporated into the planning framework. This risk analysis was carried out as part of a strategic approach to enhance the effectiveness of the residential construction schedule.

Du Plessis and Oosthuizen (2018) did extensive research to assess project management for construction plans and building contractual arrangements in South Africa. The research revealed that the standard planning circumstances used in South Africa had frameworks that were comparable to the primary construction project management skills acknowledged by the PMI. The publication also examines the broad agreements and themes of the four general circumstances of contracts supported by the Construction Industries Development Board (CIDB) in South Africa. The Construction Contract must take into account all stages of the Project Life Cycle (PLC). The Construction Contract should also be viewed as the Project Implementation Plan (PIP), upon that the construction existing controls are premised. The significance, main objective,

interdependences, and obligations of the two systems (contracts and governance) could be properly appreciated with a greater comprehension of their transformation.

When creating a construction plan, it is usual to priorities either cost control or scheduling (Sears, Sears, Clough, Rounds and Segner, 2015). A few developments are primarily divided into expense categories, each with their own set of costs. Construction planning is cost or expenditure centered in these scenarios. Within the expense classifications, a distinction is drawn between expenses involved immediately in the execution of a project and expenses incurred with indirectly in the project's successful completion. Borrowing costs for capital investment, for instance, and overhead components are frequently treated as indirect costs. Work schedules responsibilities over time are essential for several other developments and is emphasized during the strategic planning. In this case, the planner ensures that proper prioritization is sustained between many practices and that similar concepts of available resources persists. Conventional project management processes illustrate task precedence (likely to result in critical path scheduling processes) or resource efficiency over time (leading to job shop scheduling process). Eventually, most construction problems necessitate the concern of costs and schedules over time, so strategic plan, tracking, and maintaining records should take both parameters into account (Hazr, 2015). The incorporation of budget and timeline relevant data is a main consideration in these instances.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 1: The Study’s Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

The design of descriptive survey research design was employed. This design is typically structured and specific in order to describe the status of the phenomena the way it is. Rinjit, (2020) descriptive survey design describes existing phenomena through inquisition into people’s perceptions, outlooks, activities, or values and uses both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Further, the design was ideal for this study since data could be collected from a relatively large population spatially spread. Elsewhere, Cr, (2020) asserts that descriptive design collect data in testing hypotheses and answer on the current state of the subjects under study, which was applicable in this research. The implication was line with Pandey and Pandey (2021) is that this specific design studies an enormous population to reveal the project management plan and its implication on implementation of low cost housing construction projects. The researcher used descriptive research design to describe project management plan and its implication on implementation of low cost housing construction projects in Nairobi City County

The target population for this study comprise of 299 contractors and project managers involved in housing construction projects completed in Nairobi City County between the year 2020 and 2022. The target population according to Lawes, et al. (2021), a population is a collection of occurrences in that an investigator is interested and wishes to extrapolate.

Table 1: Target Population

Categories	Population
Contractors	119
Project managers	180
Total	299

Source: Nairobi City County, Kenya Government, 2022

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample size is the representative sub-set drawn from the universe for observation while sample procedure denotes the process of scientifically arriving at the representative sample (Crans, and Schuster, 2008). The study employed probability sampling methods of simple random and stratified random sampling methods. This enabled the investigator to divide the population to be sampled into strata based on the categories of either contactors or project managers and simple random level applied to select respondents for observation. Slovin’s formula was used to establish a representative sample size for the study. The formula is presented here-in;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n = Sample Size

N = Target population

e = Common Alpha Value \pm 5% and at 95% Level of Confidence

1 = Constant

$$n = \frac{299}{1 + 299(0.0025)} = 176$$

Hence, the sample size was 176 participants distributed as shown in Table 2 using a stratified sampling technique

To arrive at the study respondents, simple random procedure was employed in order to ensure that there was equal opportunity for every member of the population has equal chance of being included in the study as a participant (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2014). The researcher therefore ensured that every member of the housing company had an equal chance of being selected through randomization method. Cochran's stratified sampling approach (1977) was used to appropriate the sample.

Table 2: Sample determination

Categories	Strata Population(Ni)	$n_i = \frac{ithstratumpopulation}{targetpopulation(N)} \times n$	% of the desired sample size
Contractors (contractor with NCA1 to NCA5)	119	70	59.1%
Project managers	180	106	59.1%
Total	299	166	59.1%

Data Collection Instruments

Data was collected using self-administered questionnaires that were pretested for validity and reliability by first subjecting the instruments to the opinion of the supervisor and other experts in the industry to ascertain their content and construct validity. Reliability on the other hand according to Ogulas (2005) is the consistency of giving identical results under similar environment on repeated trials will be determined using Peason’s correlation index where values of $r = 0.7 > 1$ was applied as the desirable threshold. Cronbach Alpha was adopted for reliability tests.

Data was collected using self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 3 sections with the 3 sections collecting data on the variables and the other on demographic information of respondents. The collected data was entered into SPSS ready for transformation into meaningful information for inferences to be made on the relationship between project management plan and implementation of low cost housing construction projects. Data analysis involved descriptive statistical analysis of mean, Standard deviation, frequency counts and percentages. Inferential statistical analysis involved correlation and regression analyses to determine Karl Pearson’s correlation co-efficient and the degree, direction and level of relationship between project management plan and implementation of low cost housing construction projects.

The alpha reference level will be set at 0.05. And the regression model was presented as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y= Composite Index of implementation of low cost housing construction projects

β_0 =is a constant,

X_1 = Composite Index of project management plan

ϵ = Epsilon naught

Results and Discussion

As enlisted in the out Table ~3, an aggregate of 176(100%)- questionnaire were self-administered to all the 176 respondents. 176(82.95%) were collected from them for analysis while non-return for various reason were recorded at 30(17.05%) of the aggregate administered. Cooper and Schindler (2015) argues that surveys characterized by low response rates and when 75% and over

return rate is achieved in any survey related return response, then that is certified as an excellent response. This study achieved 82.95% response rate, consequently it was therefore an excellent rate of return for analysis and inferring.

Table 3: Questionnaire Return Rate

Questionnaires	Frequency(f)	Percent (%)
Returned'(Collected)	146	82.95
Non-Response (Retained)	30	17.05
Sum Total Questionnaire Administered	176	100.00

Descriptive Statistics of Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

This study had sought to reveal the level of implementation of low cost housing construction projects. The data outcome of descriptive statistics on implementation of low cost housing construction projects are as enlisted in output Table: ~4

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

Item.	Statements on Implementation of low cost housing construction projects	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Mean	S.D
F1	A considerably big number of low cost housing projects have been constructed	24(16.64%)	24(16.64%)	14(9.59%)	37(25.34%)	47(32.19%)	2.60	1.488
F2	The low cost housing occupancy rate has been generally high	15(10.27%)	25(17.12%)	23(15.75%)	67(45.89%)	16(10.96%)	2.70	1.182
F3	The material cost for constructing low cost housing projects is considerably low	17(11.64%)	29(19.86%)	17(11.64%)	48(32.88%)	35(23.97%)	2.62	1.350
F4	The low cost housing construction projects mortgage plans are flexible and affordable	27(18.49%)	27(18.49%)	12(8.22%)	69(47.26%)	13(8.90%)	2.88	1.302
F5	The low cost housing units constructed meet government regulatory approval for quality and safety requirements	19(13.01%)	11(7.53%)	22(15.07%)	60(41.10%)	34(23.29%)	2.46	1.287
Composite (average) Mean and S.D							2.65	1.322

The descriptive statistical analysis results as outlined in Table 4 demonstrates that implementation low cost housing construction projects can be described by a composite mean =2.65 and composite S.D=1.322 This is interpreted to mean implementation of low cost housing projects is influenced positively by statements F2, and F4, because they have means greater than composite mean of the variable. Consequently, F1, F3 and F5, negatively influenced the variable because their means were less than composite mean for the variable. Thus the negative and positive effects of the statement contributed variedly to the implementation of low cost housing construction projects.

Item F1 sought to establish if a considerably big number of low cost housing projects have been constructed. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 24(16.64%) strongly-agreed, 24(16.64%) agreed, 14(9.59%) neutral, 37(25.34%) disagreed and 47(32.19%) disagreed strongly with the statement thus suggesting that considerably big number of low cost housing projects have not been constructed. The mean score for the item statement was 2.60 and 1.488 S.D. The response frequency suggests that the implementation of low cost housing construction projects in Nairobi City County have not made substantial progress in constructing low cost houses. Item F2 sought to establish if the low cost housing occupancy rate has been generally high. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; strongly agreed, 15(10.27%) agreed, 25(17.12%) neutral, 23(15.75%) disagreed, 67(45.89%) and 16(10.96%) disagreed strongly. The statement recorded a mean of 2.70 and 1.182 S.D. The responses suggest the low cost housing occupancy rates were generally low. Item F3 sought to establish if the material cost for constructing low cost housing projects is considerably low. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; strongly-agreed 17(11.64%) agreed, 29(19.86%) neutral, 17(11.64%) disagreed 48(32.88%) and strongly-disagreed with F3 were 35(23.97%). The mean aggregate for the statement was 2.62 and 1.350 S.D. The material cost for constructing low cost housing projects were not considerably low indicating that ‘low cost’ housing projects were not actually very low. Item F4 sought to establish if the low cost housing construction projects mortgage plans are flexible and affordable. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 27(18.49%) strongly-agreed, agreed were 27(18.49%) neutrals were, 12(8.22%), 69(47.26%) disagreed and strongly-disagreed 13(8.90%) thereby scoring a mean of 2.88 and 1.302 S.D. TH results suggest that low cost housing construction projects mortgage plans were not very flexible and affordable. Item F5 sought to establish if the low cost housing units constructed meet government regulatory approval for quality and safety requirements. Of the 146 respondents who responded to the questionnaire, 19(13.01%) strongly-agreed, 11(7.53%) agreed, neutral, 22(15.07%), 60(41.10%) disagreed with another 34(23.29%) strongly-disagreed thereby scoring a mean aggregate of 2.46 and 1.2.87 S.D. The results points towards that the low cost housing units constructed were not meeting government regulatory approval for quality and safety requirements thus leading to low occupancy rates.

Project management plan and Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

The study's overall objective examined influence of project management plan on implementation of low cost housing construction projects. The resulting figures are enlisted in Table: --5

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Project Management Plan and Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

Item	Statements on Project management plan	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Mean	S.D
C1	Clear project timelines for all project phases	42(28.77%)	36(24.66%)	11(7.53%)	44(30.14%)	13(8.90%)	3.34	1.397
C2	Project milestones are well defined	32(21.92%)	51(34.93%)	21(14.38%)	36(24.66%)	6(4.11%)	3.46	1.198
C3	Clear sequence of events that incrementally built up until your project is complete	41(28.08%)	46(31.51%)	7(4.79%)	34(23.29%)	18(12.33%)	3.40	1.421
C4	Clear project implementation metrics for all project phases	42(28.77%)	42(28.77%)	13(8.90%)	34(23.29%)	15(10.27%)	3.42	1.384
C5	There is clear risk management plan	37(25.34%)	36(24.66%)	26(17.81%)	38(26.03%)	9(6.16%)	3.37	1.281
Composite Mean and S.D							3.40	1.336

The descriptive statistical analysis results as outlined in Table 5 demonstrates that project management plan can be described by a composites mean =3.40 and composite S.D=1.336. This is interpreted to mean project management plan is influenced positively by statements C2, and C4, because they have means greater than composite mean of the variable. Consequently, C1, and C5, negatively influenced the variable because their means were less than composite mean for the variable. Thus the negative and positive effects of the statement contributed variedly to the project management plan. Item C1 sought to determine if there are clear project timelines for all project phases. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 42(28.77%) strongly-agreed, 36(24.66%) agreed, 11(7.53%) neutral, 44(30.14%) disagreed, and 13(8.90%) strongly-disagreed, thereby scoring a mean of 3.34 and 1.397 S.D. The distribution mean suggests that there are clear project timelines for all project phases. Item C2 sought to determine if project milestones are well defined. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 32(21.92%)

strongly-agreed, 51(34.93%) agreed, 21(14.38%) neutral, 36(24.66%) disagreed and 6(4.11%) disagreed strongly. This item statement recorded a mean of; 3.46 and 1.198 S.D. The results suggest that to some extent project milestones can be said to be well defined and can be seen in the activity work plans. Item C3 sought to determine if clear sequence of events that incrementally built up until your project is complete. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 41(28.08%) strongly-agreed, 46(31.51%) agreed, 7(4.79%) neutral, 34(23.29%) disagreed, whereas 18(12.33%) disagreed strongly. This item statement therefore recorded a mean of 3.40 and 1.421 S.D. The outlined results suggest that to some good extent there is clear sequence of events that incrementally built up until your project is complete. Item C4 sought to determine if clear project implementation metrics for all project phases. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 42(28.77%) agreed strongly 42(28.77%) agreed, 13(8.90%) neutral, 34(23.29%) disagreed, whereas 15(10.27%) disagreed strongly. This item statement therefore recorded a mean of 3.42 and 1.384, S.D. The level of the statement contends to some agreeable there is clear project implementation metrics for all project phases. Item C5 sought to determine if there is clear risk management plan. The response distribution of the 146 respondents demonstrate that; 37(25.34%) strongly-agreed, 36(24.66%) agreed, 26(17.81%) were neutral, 38(26.03%) disagreed, and 9(6.16%) disagreed strongly. This item statement therefore recorded a mean score of 3.37 and 1.281 S.D. This suggest that to a moderately good extent there exists a clear risk management plan

Table 6: Correlations

Variable			Project Management Plan	Implementation of low cost housing construction projects
Project Management Plan	Pearson' Correlation		1	0.697**
	Sig. (2-tailed test)			0.000
	n		146.	146
Implementation of low cost housing construction projects	Pearson' Correlation		0.697**	1
	Sig. (two-tailed test)		0.000.	
	n		146	146

Alpha level at0.05

Table 6, shows that project management plan has strong, significant, positive influence on implementation of low cost housing construction projects (r=0.6971; P<0.000

Table 6: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.697 ^a	0.485	0.482	1.064

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project Management Plan

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	153.716	1	153.716	135.795	0.000 ^b
1	Residual	163.003	144	1.132		
	Total	316.719	145			

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Project Management Plan

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.570	0.240		2.377	0.019
	Project Management Plan	0.722	0.062	0.697	11.653	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Low Cost Housing Construction Projects

The (R= 0.697). Coefficient of determination results ($R^2 = 0.485$) shows that project management plan can responsibly explains 48.50% of implementation of low cost housing construction projects while the other factors not under consideration in this study accounts for 51.50%. The results also delineates that project management plan is statistically significant in predicting implementation of low cost housing construction projects because the value $P < 0.000$ compared to the alpha significant level $\alpha = 0.05$ is less and qualifies to be significant and $F = 135.795$ which is positive suggesting a positive association between the study variables. Therefore, project management plan is significant and has a positive influence on the implementation of low cost housing construction projects. project management plan as a process of integration management should thus be prepared and comprehensibly be referred to all through the project cycle as a guide to enhance implementation of low cost housing construction projects.

Summary and Conclusions

The study sought to establish influence of project management plan on implementation of low cost housing construction projects in Nairobi City County, Kenya. A significant strong positive correlation was established between project management plan on implementation of low cost housing construction projects ($r = 0.697$; $P < 0.000$). composite mean and S.D 3.40; 1.336. This implies that project management plan is a critical tool that is required in the implementation of low cost housing construction projects. It thus acts as a guide and a reference document to the project management team who should keep on using it to avoid scope creep, budget overruns and to enhance the performance of the projects.

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